

Kinetics of Oxidation of Glycollic Acid by Chromium Peroxydichromate

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The kinetics of oxidation of glycollic acid by chromium peroxydichromate has been studied. At low concentration of the substrate the order of reaction is pseudo zero and one with respect to oxidant and substrate, however, at high concentration of the substrate the respective orders are one and two. The product of oxidation is found to be formaldehyde. Influence of temperature, acids, neutral salts, Mn^{2+} and Cr^{2+} ions and solvent has been studied. A tentative mechanism has been suggested.

OXIDATION of glycollic acid has been studied with different oxidants¹⁻³. However, no attempt has been made to study its kinetics by chromium peroxydichromate (CPD). In this paper the kinetic study of glycollic acid by chromium peroxydichromate is presented. The results have been compared with those of the other oxidants.

Experimental

Glycollic acid (Riedel) and all other chemicals were of A. R. quality. Chromium peroxydichromate was prepared by a known method^{1,5}. The solutions of the reactive substances were brought to the required temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) in a thermostat, and then rapidly mixed. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and the reaction was stopped by adding ice cold distilled water. The unreacted chromium peroxydichromate was estimated iodometrically.

Results and Discussion

At low concentration of the substrate, the order of reaction is pseudo zero and one with respect to oxidant and substrate, respectively. However, at high concentration of the substrate the respective orders are one and two (Table 1 and 2).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTRATE

[CPD] = 0.0166 N		Temp. = 40°		
[GA]	$10^5 k_0$ equiv l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$\frac{10^5 k_0}{[GA]}$ min ⁻¹	$10^5 k_1$ min ⁻¹	$\frac{10^5 k_1}{[GA]^2}$ l ³ equiv ⁻³ min ⁻¹
0.10	2.51	2.51	—	—
0.20	5.10	2.55	—	—
0.30	8.09	2.69	—	—
0.40	11.54	2.86	—	—
0.80	—	—	12.86	2.09
1.00	—	—	19.73	1.97
1.25	—	—	31.53	2.01

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATION OF CPD

[CPD] × 10 ³ N	[GA] = 0.2 N $10^5 k_0$ equiv l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	[GA] = 0.8 N $10^5 k_1$ min ⁻¹
0.83	2.07	1.54
1.00	2.52	1.63
1.25	3.38	1.58
1.66	5.10	1.65
2.50	8.50	1.67
5.00	22.10	1.64

At low concentration of the substrate plot of x vs time is a straight line, while at high concentration of the substrate plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time is a straight line, indicating that the order with respect to CPD is pseudo zero and one respectively. Pseudo zero order rate constant increases with increase in the concentration of CPD, while first order rate constant is independent of the initial concentration of the oxidant.

Effect of temperature: Kinetics of oxidation of glycollic acid by CPD has been studied at different temperatures. Plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ is linear. Energy of activation (ΔE), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) have been calculated and are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

ΔE k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e u.	ΔG^\ddagger k cal mol ⁻¹
11.003	-51.35	27.72

Effect of acids: It is observed that in the presence of HCl or H₂SO₄ the reaction rate increases and further increases with increase in the concentration of the added acid (Table 4). The reason for this enhancement is that due to common ion effect the dissociation of glycollic acid is suppressed, so neutral molecule of glycollic acid is involved in the rate-determining step. If glycollate

anions were involved in the reaction then the rate would have decreased in the presence of an acid.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF HCl AND H₂SO₄ ON THE REACTION RATE
[CPD] = 0.0166 N [GA] = 0.30 N Temp. = 40°

[Acid] N	10 ³ k _o equiv l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
0.000	8.09
0.010	9.97 (9.43)
0.020	12.65 (9.88)
0.025	13.62 (11.10)
0.050	21.98 (16.26)

Values in parenthesis are in the presence of H₂SO₄.

The data in Table 4 reveal that the presence of HCl accelerates the reaction rate more than H₂SO₄ at equinormal concentration. The reason being that HCl is relatively of greater strength than H₂SO₄ and, therefore, produces more H⁺ at equinormal concentration. The presence of HCl will suppress the dissociation of glycollic acid more than H₂SO₄. Hence, HCl accelerates the reaction rate more than H₂SO₄.

Effect of neutral salts: It is observed that chlorides and sulphates of sodium and potassium have nearly no effect on the reaction rate at low ionic strength. This suggests that one of the reactants is a neutral molecule in the rate-determining step.

Effect of solvent: To study the effect of solvent, the oxidation of glycollic acid was carried out in varying percentage of acetic acid-water mixture. The rate of oxidation was found to increase with the increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture (Table 5). The plot of log k vs 1/D is linear with a positive slope, indicating that the reaction is of a positive ion-dipole type.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF SOLVENT

[GA] = 0.20 N	[CPD] = 0.01667 N	Temp. = 40°
HOAc-Water (v/v)	Dielectric constant	10 ³ k _o equiv l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
00-100	73.13*	5.10
10-90	66.07	7.27
20-80	59.64	9.51
30-70	53.48	11.84
40-60	46.31	15.50
50-50	39.62	20.81

* Calculated from the relation log ε = 1.9461 - 0.00205 × t

Effect of Mn^{II} ion: It is observed that in the presence of Mn^{II} ions the reaction rate is retarded (Table 6). This is expected if Mn^{II} ions catalyse the disproportionation of intermediate valence state of chromium and indicates that Cr^{IV} is probably involved as an intermediate.

Effect of Cr^{III} ion: It is observed that in the presence of added Cr^{III} ions the reaction is retarded (Table 7). The reason being that Cr^{III}

ions possibly form complex with glycollic acid. Thus the decrease in the concentration of glycollic acid lowers the value of the rate constant.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF Mn^{II} IONS

[GA] = 0.30 N	[CPD] = 0.0166 N	Temp. = 40°
Mn ²⁺ × 10 ³ M	10 ³ k _o equiv l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	
0.0	8.09	
1.0	7.68	
2.0	7.51	
4.0	7.32	

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF Cr^{III} IONS

[GA] = 0.30 N	[CPD] = 0.0166 N	Temp. = 40°
[Cr ^{III} acetate. H ₂ O] × 10 ³ M	10 ³ k _o equiv dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	
0.0	8.09	
5.0	7.81	
7.5	7.69	
10.0	7.53	

The product of oxidation in excess substrate concentration is formaldehyde, which has been identified by preparing its dimedone derivative¹⁴ and by its characteristic spot test¹⁵.

Mechanism: Chromium peroxydichromate is known to decompose in aqueous solution as

From the proposed mechanism the derived rate laws are

$$-\frac{d[\text{CPD}]}{dt} = k[\text{GA}][\text{CPD}]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{for low concentration of substrate}$$

$$\text{and } -\frac{d[\text{CPD}]}{dt} = k^1[\text{GA}]^2[\text{CPD}] \quad \text{for high concentration of substrate}$$

These rate laws are in agreement with the experimental observations.

Thermodynamic parameters and kinetic process : The rate of reaction is not determined solely by the energy of activation (ΔE), since the frequency factor can vary over a considerable range. It is the free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger), which determines the rate of reaction at a given temperature. Higher the ΔG^\ddagger , the slower is the reaction rate¹⁶ at a given temperature. If entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) is negative, the activated complex is less probable and the rate is slower¹⁷. Thus the large negative entropy of activation and high free energy of activation (Table 3) mean a slow reaction, which is in agreement with the observed smaller specific rate constant. The negative value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates the reaction should be between similarly charged ions or between a charged ion and a neutral molecule¹⁸. Thus the calculated thermodynamic parameters explain the kinetic process.

Comparison of kinetics and mechanism of glycollic acid oxidation by CPD with other oxidants : The order of reaction between glycollic acid and CPD is pseudo zero and one with respect to oxidant and substrate, respectively at low concentration of the substrate, while at high concentration of the substrate the respective orders are one and two. However, with other oxidants the order of reaction is one with respect to both the oxidant and the substrate. The entropy of activation for the reaction investigated is large negative (Table 3), while with most of the other oxidants it is either positive or small negative.

The present investigation reveals that the change in ionic strength has nearly no effect on the rate of reaction in dilute solution. However, in case of most of the other oxidants the change in ionic strength has a definite retarding influence on the reaction rate.

The effect of dielectric constant of the medium was studied with a limited number of oxidants. In chromic acid² oxidation of glycollic acid, no relationship between logarithm of rate constant and dielectric constant of the medium was established. In lead tetra-acetate⁹ oxidation of glycollic acid, on the basis of effect of dielectric constant on the reaction rate, the reaction of dipole-dipole type was suggested. However, the effect of dielectric constant on the rate of oxidation of glycollic acid by CPD shows that the reaction is of a positive ion-dipole type.

Oxidation of glycollic acid with some oxidants showed a kinetic evidence regarding the complex

formation between glycollic acid and the oxidising species. However, no such evidence was observed for the present reaction as Michael Menton's plot of $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{GA}]$ does not give a positive intercept on Y axis.

The product of oxidation of glycollic acid by CPD is formaldehyde, while with the other oxidants it was found to be either glyoxalic acid or oxalate ion or formic acid or formaldehyde.

The mechanism of oxidation of glycollic acid by other oxidants^{1,2,4,7} involved either rupture of α -C-H bond or rupture of C-C bond in the rate-determining step. In case of some oxidants¹⁹⁻²² the slow step involved the decomposition of the complex into free radicals. However, the proposed mechanism of oxidation of glycollic acid by chromium peroxydichromate involves two electron transfer from the reductant, glycollic acid, to the oxidising species, Cr^{VI} in the rate-determining step. The proposed mechanism is, however, similar to that suggested for the oxidation of lactic acid by chromium peroxydichromate²³.

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